

On Mach's principle, Dirac's large number hypothesis and the origin of fundamental physical constants

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Abstract

This paper explores the implications of Mach's principle and Dirac's large number hypothesis, aiming to quantitatively describe the influence of universal mass distribution on local gravitation and electromagnetic dynamics, while exploring its connection to the origin of fundamental physical constants.

Section (I) aims to demonstrate that the relation $G \cong \frac{c^2 R_u}{M_u}$ may in fact hold with remarkable precision. By deriving an equation to estimate the radius R_u and mass M_u of the observable universe, as well as the Hubble constant H_0 using the equation for G and a proposed equation for the fine structure constant $\alpha_f = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{r_p^2}{R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_p}$, I reach a relativistic equation of gravitational potential capable of predicting the observed cosmological redshift. This model attributes the redshift to the cumulative mass within the volume defined by the distance light has traveled from its source.

Section (II) aims to shed light on the problem of galaxy rotation curves and presents a plausible origin for the MOND constant $a_0 \cong 1.2E - 10 \text{ m/s}^2$, characterized by the mass surface density relation of the observable universe over that of the galaxy. I derive an equation for the local system's total relativistic energy as $E_t = m_l c^2 \sqrt{1 + \frac{r_l^2}{2\pi R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_l}}$, and incorporate a momentum component resulting from the local system's rotation relative to the distant masses of the universe.

Section (III) develops an interconnected set of equations based on the calculation of the fine structure constant as the mass surface density relation of the observable universe to that of the proton $\alpha_f = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{r_p^2}{R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_p}$, and the Rydberg constant $R_\infty = \frac{m_e}{m_p} \frac{\alpha_f^2}{\pi r_p}$ to precisely calculate fundamental constants of electromagnetism (e , ϵ_0 , μ_0 , and h). I apply these to calculate the proton-electron mass ratio, and the relative strength of the gravitation and electromagnetic forces.

Section (IV) presents a set of equations that emerge from the previous section, potentially providing insights into a relation between nuclear and electromagnetic forces. Specifically, I describe a quantitative relationship between electromagnetic potential, α_f , the rest mass energy of the proton and electron, and the ranges of nuclear strong and weak forces. Finally, I find that the relative strength of the strong, weak, electromagnetic, and gravitational forces can be described quantitatively as a function of α_f as the mass surface density relation.

Section I: On the origin of Newton's gravitational constant G and the Hubble constant H₀

Mach's Principle and Gravitational Constant G

Since the late nineteenth century and well into the mid-twentieth century, several influential thinkers put forth the notion that local gravitational and inertial dynamics are not solely determined by the local distribution of mass and energy, but also by the state of the entire cosmos. This idea, known as Mach's principle, has been explored in depth by a number of luminaries in the field, including Mach (Mach, 1883), Einstein (Einstein, 1916), Schrödinger (Schrödinger, 1925), Dirac (Dirac, 1937), Eddington (Eddington, 1938), Sciama (Sciama, 1953), Dicke (Dicke, 1961) and others. A central conclusion that emerges from their works is that the gravitational constant G is determined by the distribution of all mass throughout the observable universe. The conceptual development, historic contributions of this idea, and its consequences for physical theory are clearly presented in A. Unzicker's book "Einstein's Lost Key" (Unzicker, 2022). This idea has important implications for our understanding of the fundamental nature of gravity and the structure of the cosmos. The equation which quantifies this idea is the following:

$$G \cong \frac{c^2 R_u}{M_u}$$

In this equation, G is the gravitational constant with the value 6.67430(15)E-11 N·kg⁻²·m² (CODATA 2018). c² is the speed of light squared. The values R_u and M_u are the radius of the observable universe and the mass enclosed within a sphere of volume (V_u) by $V_u = \frac{4}{3}\pi R_u^3$. This equation is a correct relation within orders of magnitude for the current estimates of the radius of the observable universe and the mass enclosed in its volume. I hope to contribute here to the demonstration that it is in fact a precise relation and $G = \frac{c^2 R_u}{M_u}$.

In the 1930s, Paul Dirac published his finding of an intriguing approximate relation, given the estimated values at the time, between the ratios of the electrostatic and gravitational force, and the ratios of the radii and masses of the universe and the proton. It is known as Dirac's Large Number Hypothesis.

$$\frac{F_e}{F_g} \approx \frac{R_u}{r_p} \approx 10^{39} \quad \text{and} \quad \frac{R_u^2}{r_p^2} \approx \frac{M_u}{m_p} \approx 10^{78}$$

He described this coincidence by stating that "*such a coincidence we may presume is due to some deep connection in nature between cosmology and atomic theory.*" (Dirac, 1937)

In this work of exploration of the origin of fundamental physical constants, I have found that the ratio of the mass surface density of the observable universe and that of the proton may be at the heart of cosmological as well as atomic phenomena. Moreover, this ratio seems to determine the ratio of the strength of physical forces. The equation that is at the centre of this idea is the one I derive for the fine structure constant α_f .

$$\alpha_f = \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 \hbar c} = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{r_p^2}{R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_p}$$

To test these equations, one can imagine the entire mass of the observable universe as contained in a thin spherical shell around any given body. The mass of this universal shell is equal to the total mass M_u contained within the volume determined by the radius of the sphere R_u .

Following Newton's shell theorem, a body inside this massive shell would feel a net zero gravitational acceleration, as the forces on this body from the massive shell would all cancel out. The body would however be present in a gravitational potential. If this potential is $U_u = c^2$, then it would mean that the rest mass energy of all objects mc^2 arises in its totality from the gravitational potential of the massive universal shell.

$$\text{Since } G = \frac{c^2 R_u}{M_u} \quad \text{then } U_u = \frac{GM_u}{R_u} = c^2$$

Hubble's Constant H_0

Hubble's constant H_0 is measured in units of km/s/Mpc. Its value is determined largely by two groups of methods. The first group essentially measures a value of H_0 based on measurements and known luminosity-distance relations in the local universe. The second group derives the value of H_0 by applying the current cosmological model to observations of the Cosmic Background Radiation (CMB).

Riess et al. (Riess, 2022) apply the distance ladder method to measure redshift of known luminosity-distance relations in the local universe and reach a value for $H_0=73.30(\pm 1.04)$ km/s/Mpc. The Planck Collaboration 2018 (Planck Collaboration, 2020) analyses the CMB radiation to predict a value of $H_0=67.4 (\pm 0.5)$ km/s/Mpc. These latest values lie outside of their respective uncertainty ranges. Therefore, the current measurement of H_0 from the local universe, and the prediction using the current cosmological model and the CMB currently do not agree.

Hubble's constant H_0 is used for determining the expected cosmological redshift from a given distance. It is interpreted as the redshift from the recessional velocities of galaxies due to the universe's expansion.

I propose that it may instead be the measure of the aggregate gravitational redshift of light propagating from its source through an increasing gravitational potential. This increasing potential proportional to the distance travelled by the light is due to the increasing amounts of mass enclosed in the volume defined by a radius equal to the distance travelled.

I propose that one can derive a relation between the Hubble constant H_0 and the gravitational potential of the universe as follows.

$$\text{If } U_u = \frac{GM_u}{R_u} = H_0 R_u \quad \text{then } H_0 = \frac{U_u}{R_u} = \frac{c^2}{R_u}$$

The units of H_0 in this equation are m/s^2 . Therefore, I must first convert the units from km/s/Mpc to units of acceleration m/s^2 . I can convert the units from km to metres and from Mpc to light seconds to obtain the correct units of acceleration m/s^2 and define the values of H_0 for both Riess et al. and Planck Collaboration with these units.

$$\text{Riess et al. 2022} \quad H_0 = 7.1215434727854E - 10 \frac{m}{s^2}$$

$$\text{Planck Collaboration 2018} \quad H_0 = 6.54832237470308E - 10 \frac{m}{s^2}$$

I propose here that the value is in fact $H_0 \cong 75.43 \text{ Km/s/Mpc}$. I have arrived at this value by applying the following relations found in this Section I, and in Section III on electromagnetic constants.

In this Section I, I can express the ratio of the mass over radius of the universe as follows.

$$\text{Since } G = \frac{c^2 R_u}{M_u} \quad \text{therefore} \quad \frac{M_u}{R_u} = \frac{c^2}{G}$$

In Section III, I reach the following equation from the fine structure constant α_f , as the ratio of the mass surface density of the observable universe over the mass surface density of the proton and obtain a relation for the ratio of the mass over the radius squared of the observable universe.

$$\text{Since } \alpha_f = \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 \hbar c} = \frac{\pi r_p^2 M_u}{2 R_u^2 m_p} \quad \text{therefore} \quad \frac{M_u}{R_u^2} = \alpha_f \frac{2 m_p}{\pi r_p^2}$$

I can then combine these ratio equations to obtain an equation for the radius of the observable universe.

$$\text{Since } R_u = \frac{\frac{M_u}{R_u}}{\frac{M_u}{R_u^2}} = \frac{\frac{c^2}{G}}{\alpha_f \frac{2 m_p}{\pi r_p^2}} \quad \text{therefore} \quad R_u = \frac{c^2 r_p^2 \pi 1}{G m_p 2 \alpha_f} = \sim 1.23E + 26 \text{ m}$$

And finally, I can use this equation for the radius of the observable universe to reach the calculated value of H_0 as follows.

$$\text{Since } H_0 = \frac{U_u}{R_u} = \frac{c^2}{R_u} \quad \text{therefore} \quad H_0 = \frac{c^2}{\frac{c^2 r_p^2 \pi 1}{G m_p 2 \alpha_f}} = \frac{G m_p 2}{r_p^2 \pi} \alpha_f$$

$$\text{And } H_0 = \sim 7.33E - 10 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2} \quad \text{and} \quad H_0 = \sim 75.43 \frac{\text{km}}{\text{s Mpc}}$$

The relation that emerges from the equation for H_0 is the product of the gravitational acceleration on the surface of a proton and the fine structure constant. This is of course correct as the equation is derived from the mass surface ratio relation.

$$H_0 = \frac{G m_p 2}{r_p^2 \pi} \alpha_f = \frac{G m_p}{r_p^2} \frac{r_p^2 M_u}{R_u^2 m_p} = \frac{G M_u}{R_u^2} = \frac{c^2}{R_u}$$

I can apply the equations above to also estimate the total mass of the observable universe and therefore its mass volume density.

Regarding the mass of the universe M_u , Fukugita et al. (Fukugita, 1998) estimated it to be $1.5E+53$ kg. The Planck Collaboration in 2016 (Planck Collaboration, 2016) published an estimate of $4.9E+52$ kg (± 0.1) for the total baryonic mass of the universe M_u . I can calculate it using the following equation.

$$M_u = \frac{H_0 R_u^2}{G} = \sim 1.65E + 53 \text{ kg}$$

The total density of the universe at large scales, with radius larger than 500 Mpc, it is expected by current cosmology to be close to or equal to the critical density. The Planck Collaboration (Planck Collaboration, 2016) estimates the critical density ρ_{crit} as $\rho_{\text{crit}}=9.6E-27 \text{ kg/m}^3$. I obtain a value for the universe's constant density at large scales which is twice that of the Planck Collaboration.

$$\rho_u = \frac{M_u}{\frac{4}{3}\pi R_u^3} = \sim 2.14E - 26 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$$

It is important to note that if one assumes that G and c^2 do not change over time, as all evidence so far indicates, then the equations of this Section and all the following require that R_u remains constant over time.¹ We already know we do not exist in a special location in the universe. If the universe is expanding, it would mean that we live in a truly special moment in time. A time when all the equations in this work hold true only with today's value of R_u .

Cosmological Gravitational Redshift

Applying once more Newtown's Shell Theorem which also shows us that a spherically symmetric object affects other objects gravitationally as if all its mass were concentrated at its centre, I propose that cosmological redshift arises from the gravitational field of the total baryonic mass enclosed within the volume determined by a radius equal to the distance the light has travelled.

To visualise this, I imagine the source of the light, for example a star in a distant galaxy, to be surrounded by concentric massive shells. As the light propagates towards us, it crosses more and more massive shells, leaving behind a spherically symmetric volume of mass. This volume of mass will produce gravitational redshift effectively reducing the energy of the light. One would expect as well, using General Relativity, a proportional time dilation effect on the propagating light.

If this is true, then light traveling from a distant point measured locally would necessary be affected by a gravitational potential which is proportional to the radius r as the distance travelled, and the mass enclosed within the volume determined by that radius r . One should be able to calculate this gravitational redshift with the well-known function $\frac{G m}{c^2 r}$.

I propose that these equations can be used to predict the cosmological redshift observed using the following relativistic redshift formula to calculate the value of redshift z using this aggregate gravitational potential from all the mass enclosed in the volume determined by a radius equal to the distance travelled by the light.

$$z = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{G m}{c^2 r}}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{G m}{c^2 r}}} - 1 = \frac{\sqrt{1 + \frac{m R_u}{r M_u}}}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{m R_u}{r M_u}}} - 1$$

¹ The only option where R_u can change over time is if we postulate that the mass of the universe M_u is also changing directly proportionally over time to keep the *ratio* of R_u/M_u constant. I cannot find any plausible evidence for this constant increase of M_u needed to keep up with the expansion of R_u and it would violate the law of conservation of energy. Therefore, I consider this option highly unlikely.

We can see that the redshift is determined by the ratio of gravitational potentials from the volume travelled over the total observable universe volume.

The graph below shows the redshift value z and distance measured in billions of light years predicted by this equation. The value of z increases exponentially for my equation for relativistic gravitational redshift as the distance approaches the radius of the observable universe R_u at ~ 12.963 billion light years.

The source of data for the two standard cosmology redshift curves for $H_0=73.3$ and $H_0=67.4$ is the Cosmological Calculator for the Flat Universe by Nick Gnedin from the Department of Astronomy and Astrophysics of the University of Chicago².

Distance Relation from the Density of the Universe

Assuming a homogenous and isotropic universe at large scales with constant total density, I should be able to use the value of this constant density of ρ_u as the predicted constant density of the universe at scales of radius 500 Mpc or larger (~ 1.631 billion light years) to estimate the total mass enclosed in a volume of a given radius starting with 500 Mpc. I am using 500 Mpc to account

² Cosmological Calculator for the Flat Universe by Nick Gnedin: <https://astro.uchicago.edu/~gnedin/cc/>

for peculiar velocities of individual galaxies and the density variations within nearby clusters of galaxies and local voids.

The mass within any given volume with radius larger than 500 Mpc is not necessarily homogenous and isotropic within its given volume, as we have seen by the observations of structures like the “Giant Arc” and “Big Ring”³. The total density at these scales however would hold.

This would mean that for observations at distances r larger than 500 Mpc, I can replace the local mass m by the product of the constant density and volume enclosed by $m = \rho_u \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3$. I can also replace the total mass of the universe M_u by $M_u = \rho_u \frac{4}{3} \pi R_u^3$. In this way, I can simplify further my equation, for large enough scales where $r > 500 \text{Mpc}$, by replacing m and M_u . I obtain an equation which can calculate the cosmological redshift as a simple function of the ratio of the distance from the source over the radius of the observable universe.

$$z = \frac{1 + \sqrt{\frac{\rho_u \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 R_u}{\rho_u \frac{4}{3} \pi r R_u^3}}}{1 - \sqrt{\frac{\rho_u \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 R_u}{\rho_u \frac{4}{3} \pi r R_u^3}}} - 1 = \frac{1 + \sqrt{\frac{r^2}{R_u^2}}}{1 - \sqrt{\frac{r^2}{R_u^2}}} - 1 = \frac{1 + \frac{r}{R_u}}{1 - \frac{r}{R_u}} - 1$$

Underdensity of Local Universe

This model would predict cosmic variance in the value of H_0 depending on the density of the volume of space.⁴ If we can measure at the right scale of radius (above 50 and below 500 Mpc for example) a significant variation from this constant density ρ_u , either of a smaller density (for example a volume including the Northern Local Supervoid), or a larger density (for example a volume including the Perseus-Pices Supercluster), we should observe a proportional variation of the value of H_0 .

In fact, the measured value for H_0 from Reiss et al. 2022 of 73.3 km/s/Mpc compared to this work’s prediction of ~ 75.43 km/s/Mpc would predict a proportional mass underdensity ρ_l within the local volume of measurement from Reiss et al. work as compared to the constant density ρ_u of the observable universe at larger scales.

$$\text{Since at } H_0 = \sim 75.43 \quad \text{then} \quad \rho_u = \frac{M_u}{\frac{4}{3} \pi R_u^3} = \sim 2.14E - 26 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$$

$$\text{Then at } H_0 = \sim 73.3 \quad \text{then} \quad \rho_l = \frac{m_l}{\frac{4}{3} \pi r_l^3} = \sim 1.96E - 26 \frac{\text{kg}}{\text{m}^3}$$

³ University of Central Lancashire (UCLan) Ph.D. student Alexia Lopez, discoverer of both the “Giant Arc” and “Big Ring” presented her findings on the Big Ring at the 243rd meeting of the American Astronomical Society (AAS) on 10 January 2024.

⁴ An interesting investigation of cosmic variance can be found in the work of Hill, C. J., MacCrann, N., Raghunathan, S., Kovacs, A., Palmese, A., Avila, S., ... & Zhang, B. in 2021 (Hill, 2021)

Cosmic Background Radiation (CMB)

Finally, a point regarding the Cosmic Microwave Background (CMB) which I find interesting. The current understanding is that the expected temperature of the CMB at its origin (time of decoupling) is approximately 3,000 K (Peebles, 1982) and the redshift due to the Hubble expansion has a value of $z \sim 1,100$. This redshift reduces its frequency and therefore temperature to the observed of 2.7 K today (Fixsen, 2007). It is interesting to note that a temperature of 3,000 K is within the range of the average surface temperature of the most common stars in the universe: stars of spectral class M which range from 2,000 K for cool red dwarfs to less than 3,500 K for all stars in this class. The equations presented here, with a z value input of $z \sim 1,100$ would place this oldest observable light at ~ 12.96 billion light years, or just ~ 21 thousand light years from the maximum observable distance of R_u .

Section II: On the origin of the MOND constant a_0

In 1912, Einstein explores the idea of an induction-like effect of gravitation for a body placed within a hollow massive shell, when the body or the shell are accelerated (Einstein, 1912). In his work "On the origin of inertia", Sciama (Sciama, 1953) also proposes that the dynamics of a body in rotation would be affected by the large-scale distribution of mass of the universe.

If the energy content of all massive bodies arises from the universal gravitational potential, and their inertia arises from their gravitational interaction with the rest of the universe, it would mean that the momentum (linear and angular) of any massive body also includes their gravitational coupling with all the masses in the rest of the universe. Therefore, any accelerated motion would be influenced by this interaction.

Observational data has demonstrated that the rotation of galaxies and clusters of galaxies deviate from the predictions of both Newtonian and General Relativity gravitation, if based only on the total baryonic mass estimated to be contained within them. The hypothesis to address this discrepancy in the standard cosmological model is the existence of dark matter, a form of matter which does not interact electromagnetically but contributes substantially to the total mass of galaxies and clusters of galaxies.

In the 1980s, M. Milgrom's developed Modified Newtonian Dynamics (MOND). In his paper titled "A Modification of the Newtonian Dynamics as a Possible Alternative to the Hidden Mass Hypothesis" (Milgrom, 1983), Milgrom proposes an alternative to the hypothesis of dark matter to explain the observed mass discrepancies in galaxies. He suggested that, at low accelerations ($< \sim 10^{-10} \text{ m/s}^2$), the acceleration of an object is determined by a modification of Newton's second law of motion, which he called MOND. In empirical terms, MOND departs from standard dynamics at accelerations smaller than $a_0 \cong 1.2\text{E-}10 \text{ m/s}^2$ which is a new constant with the dimensions of acceleration that MOND introduces into physics.

In MOND, the total modified acceleration of gravity which I will note as a_m is related to the ratio of the MOND constant a_0 and the Newtonian acceleration a_N . The most commonly used functional expression for a_m can be written as follows.

$$a_m = a_N \sqrt{1 + \left(\frac{a_0^2}{a_N^2}\right)}$$

Here a_m =total modified acceleration, a_N =Newtonian acceleration, and a_0 =MOND constant= $1.2E-10$ m/s². As this equation is mathematically equivalent to $a_m^2 = a_N^2 + a_0^2$, it is limited by the largest value of the two squared variables and will not give the correct predictions when $a_N \ll a_0$.

The following expression can be used at the weak acceleration limit where $a_N \ll a_0$.

$$a_m = \sqrt{a_N a_0} = \sqrt{G m a_0 / r}$$

Finally, to have a continuous function for MOND which works seamlessly from the Newtonian regime scales through to the weak acceleration limit, the following equation can be used from the MOND introductory review paper by R. Scarpa from 2006 (Scarpa, 2006).

$$a_m = a_N \sqrt{1/2 + 1/2 \sqrt{1 + (4a_0^2/a_N^2)}}$$

To explore the origin of the MOND constant a_0 I will first define the problem in terms of energy. The energy-momentum relation equation for the total relativistic energy E_t of an object includes both its rest energy and its kinetic energy is given by the following expression.

$$E_t^2 = (mc^2)^2 + (pc)^2$$

I propose that all local rotating systems include a component of their momentum which is due to its interaction with the rest of the masses of the universe, and that the MOND ratio a_0/a_N effectively predicts this component of a local systems momentum.

Milgrom (Milgrom, 2008) already identified that there seems to be a correlation between H_0 and a_0 as described by $a_0 \approx c H_0/2\pi$. Applying the value presented in Section I of H_0 in units of m/s², we can obtain the following result.

$$\frac{H_0}{2\pi} = \frac{c^2}{2\pi R_u} \cong 1.17E - 10 \frac{m}{s^2}$$

This value is clearly very close to the effective value found by MOND. One can see that the expression has the form of a tangential acceleration $\frac{v^2}{2\pi r}$ which is determined by the circumference of the massive shell of the universe around the local system $2\pi R_u$, and the relative tangential velocity of the system with the massive shell at R_u where $v = c$.

When I combine a_0 with a_N to obtain the MOND ratio function, I reach following expression with m_l as the local system's baryonic mass, and r_l its radius.

$$\frac{a_0}{a_N} = \frac{\frac{c^2}{2\pi R_u}}{\frac{G m_l}{r_l^2}} = \frac{\frac{c^2}{2\pi R_u}}{\frac{c^2 R_u}{M_u} \frac{m_l}{r_l^2}} = \frac{r_l^2}{2\pi R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_l}$$

I find that the final function is determined by the ratio of the surface mass density of the universe and the surface mass density of the local system, with a factor of $\frac{1}{2\pi}$.

Once again, the ratio of the mass surface density of the universe over that of the local system seems to be an important element of the local dynamics. I propose that this function influences the local system's total momentum and therefore its total relativistic energy.

$$\text{Where momentum} \quad p = m_l v = m_l c \sqrt{\frac{r_l^2}{2\pi R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_l}}$$

$$\text{Since} \quad E_t^2 = (m_l c^2)^2 + (p c)^2$$

$$\text{Therefore} \quad E_t^2 = (m_l c^2)^2 + \left(m_l c^2 \sqrt{\frac{r_l^2}{2\pi R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_l}} \right)^2$$

$$\text{And} \quad E_t = m_l c^2 \sqrt{1 + \frac{r_l^2}{2\pi R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_l}}$$

Using this equation, I can derive an expression for the dynamical mass m_d of the local system which is determined by its total relativistic energy.

$$\text{Dynamical mass of the local system} \quad m_d = \frac{E_t}{c^2} = m_l \sqrt{1 + \frac{r_l^2}{2\pi R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_l}}$$

Given that low acceleration regimes do not require General Relativity corrections, I can use this equation for the dynamical mass of the local system to derive an expression for the modified acceleration a_m using the Newtonian gravitational acceleration a_N .

$$\text{Modified Gravity from Dynamical Mass} \quad a_m = \frac{G m_d}{r_l^2} = a_N \sqrt{1 + \frac{r_l^2}{2\pi R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_l}}$$

The empirical success of MOND has been demonstrated by extensive research by S. McGaugh who, among many papers, published in 2016 a paper titled "The Radial Acceleration Relation in Rotationally Supported Galaxies" (McGaugh, 2016). In this paper, McGaugh et. al. analysed a sample of 153 galaxies with well-resolved kinematics and found a tight correlation between the radial acceleration of baryons and the observed acceleration, which includes the contribution of dark matter. This correlation, known as the Radial Acceleration Relation (RAR), suggests that dark matter would not be necessary to explain the observed dynamics of galaxies.

In the following graph I present the predicted values using the dynamical mass equation I derived above, compared to those when using the MOND Scarpa 2006 equation, as well as the equation for the MOND weak acceleration limit.

I find that this dynamical mass model derived from a local systems total relativistic energy agrees with high precision with those predicted by MOND. Moreover, my equation provides a simple continuous function which seamlessly predicts acceleration from the Newtonian regime to scales when $a_N \ll a_0$.

$$\text{MOND Weak Acceleration Limit} \quad a_m = \sqrt{a_N a_0}$$

$$\text{MOND Scarpa 2006} \quad a_m = a_N \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{1 + \left(4a_0^2/a_N^2\right)}}$$

$$\text{Dynamical Mass Model from } E_t \quad a_m = \frac{G m_d}{r_l^2} = a_N \sqrt{1 + \frac{r_l^2}{2\pi R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_l}}$$

It is important to note that, for galaxy clusters, both MOND and this dynamical mass equation reduce greatly the observed mass discrepancy: from a factor of ~ 10 , required by standard dynamics, to a factor of about 2. However, this systematic remnant discrepancy is yet to be conclusively accounted for (Milgrom, 2015). Moreover, in 2023, Banik et al. (Banik, 2024) tested MOND using wide binary stars and argues that MOND must be substantially modified on small scales to account for local wide binaries.

Regarding the systematic discrepancy for clusters of galaxies, it is certainly plausible, given the large uncertainties in our models, that it may be due simply to an under estimation of the total baryonic mass contained within them, especially from intergalactic gas. It is perhaps interest to

note that in the previous Section, I reach a value of the density within the observable universe which is approximately two times larger than the critical density estimated for a flat universe.

Regarding the wide binary stars systems. I would propose an analysis based on the total mass surface density ratio of the entire binary system to obtain the system's total relativistic energy, and therefore equivalent mass. In the case of a galaxy, the orbiting star's mass is many orders of magnitude smaller than the total mass of the galaxy and therefore can be neglected. This would not be the case for a binary star system with orbiting stars of similar masses to each other.

Section III: On the origin of constants of electromagnetism

In this section, I will aim to derive equations to calculate the fundamental constants of electromagnetism, and to apply these equations to explore the relationship between the forces of electromagnetism and gravitation. Once again, I find that the function of the ratio of the mass surface density of the universe over the proton in this case is at the centre of my findings.

The following table includes a list of the latest available values for selected constants from CODATA (2018), Riess et al.(2022) for the value for the Hubble constant H_0 , the derived radius and mass of the universe, as well as the MOND constant a_0 using the models of Section I and II.

Table of CODATA 2018 values for selected fundamental constants⁵

Description	Source	Notation	Units	Value
Speed of light in vacuum	CODATA 2018 (exact)	c	m·s ⁻¹	299,792,458
Hubble Constant (in km·s ⁻¹ ·Mpc ⁻¹)	Reiss 2022 (± 1.04)	H _{0,Mpc}	km·s ⁻¹ ·Mpc ⁻¹	73.30
Hubble Constant (in m·s ⁻²)	H _{0,Mpc} in meters/seconds ²	H ₀	m·s ⁻²	7.12154347E-10
Radius Universe	R _u = c ² / H ₀	R _u	m	1.26202302E+26
Mass Universe	M _u = H ₀ ·R _u ² /G	M _u	Kg	1.69942874E+53
G Gravitational constant	CODATA 2018 (0.00015E-11)	G	m ³ ·kg ⁻¹ ·s ⁻²	6.6743E-11
a ₀ MOND constant	Milgrom 1994 (± 0.2)	a ₀	m·s ⁻²	1.20E-10
Proton mass	CODATA 2018 (0.00000000051E-27)	m _p	Kg	1.67262192369E-27
Proton charge radius	CODATA 2018 (0.019E-16)	r _p	M	8.414E-16
Electron mass	CODATA 2018 (0.0000000028E-31)	m _e	Kg	9.1093837015E-31
Electron classical radius	CODATA 2018 (0.0000000013E-15)	r _e	m	2.8179403262E-15
Electron Bohr radius (1s hydrogen orbital)	CODATA 2018 (0.00000000080E-11)	r _{1s}	m	5.29177210903E-11
Proton to Electron mass ratio	CODATA 2018 (0.00000011)	m _p /m _e	<i>dimensionless</i>	1836.15267343
h Planck constant	CODATA 2018 (exact)	h	kg·m ² ·s ⁻¹	6.62607015E-34
α _f Fine structure constant	CODATA 2018 (0.0000000011E-3)	α _f	<i>dimensionless</i>	7.2973525693E-03
e elementary charge	CODATA 2018 (exact)	e	C	1.602176634E-19
ε ₀ Vacuum electric permittivity	CODATA 2018 (0.0000000013E-12)	ε ₀	F·m ⁻¹	8.8541878128E-12
μ ₀ Vacuum magnetic permeability	CODATA 2018(0.00000000019E-6)	μ ₀	N·A ⁻²	1.25663706212E-06
Rydberg Constant R _∞	CODATA 2018(0.000021)	R _∞	m ⁻¹	10,973,731.56816
Rydberg Constant for Hydrogen R _H	R _H = (m _p / (m _p + m _e)) * R _∞	R _H	m ⁻¹	10,967,758.3402804

⁵ CODATA 2018 values of fundamental constants: <https://physics.nist.gov/cuu/Constants/index.html>

The following table presents my calculated adjusted values for the proton and electron masses, their ratio, and their respective radii. All the values are within the uncertainty values of CODATA (2018). I arrive to all of them through the interdependent relations of the equations developed in this Section. The equation that anchors the determination of these values is the one I derive for the Rydberg constant R_∞ . The starting point is the determination of the value of radius of the proton, taking the mass ratio of electron to proton, and the fine structure constant values from CODATA to solve the equation of R_∞ with a precise result.

$$\text{Since } R_\infty = \frac{m_e e^4}{8 \epsilon_0^2 h^3 c} = \frac{m_e \alpha_f^2}{m_p \pi r_p} = 10,973,731.56816 \text{ m}^{-1}$$

$$\text{Therefore } r_p = \frac{m_e \alpha_f^2}{m_p \pi R_\infty} = 8.41235641340976E - 16 \text{ m}$$

Table of calculated values for the proton and electron

Description	Notation	Units	Value
Proton mass	m_p	kg	1.67262192369251E-27
Proton charge radius	r_p	m	8.41235641340976E-16
Electron mass	m_e	kg	9.10938370151773E-31
Electron classical radius	r_e	m	2.81794032620793E-15
Electron Bohr radius	r_{1s}	m	5.29177210903463E-11
Proton to Electron mass ratio	m_p/m_e	<i>dimensionless</i>	1836.15267343918

The next table has my calculated the values for the Hubble constant and consequent mass and radius of the universe, all of which have a variation of $\sim \pm 2.9\%$ from the reported value of $H = 73.3 \text{ km}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Mpc}^{-1}$ (Reiss 2022). These adjustments are outside of the uncertainty reported by Reiss. The table has also my calculated value for the MOND constant a_0 which is smaller than the standard MOND by $\sim -2.9\%$.

Table of calculated values for selected cosmological constants

Description	Notation	Units	Value
Hubble Constant (in $\text{km}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Mpc}^{-1}$)	$H_{0,\text{Mpc}}$	$\text{km}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}\cdot\text{Mpc}^{-1}$	75.4298904525255
Hubble Constant (in $\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$)	H_0	$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$	7.32847536159756E-10
Radius Universe	R_u	m	1.22638766508849E+26
Mass Universe	M_u	kg	1.65144249604788E+53
MOND constant	a_0	$\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$	1.16636307912542E-10

Planck Constant h and the Fine Structure Constant α_f

It is well known that the units of h are equivalent to the units of angular momentum: $\text{J}\cdot\text{Hz}^{-1} = \text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. We also know the electron is a matter wave which follows the De Broglie relation between wavelength and momentum $p = h / \lambda$ or $h = p \cdot \lambda$. Therefore, given that h has the units of angular momentum, and assuming h_e is the angular momentum of the electron in the 1s orbital as Bohr did, the equation would be $h_e = \text{mass of the electron (kg)} \cdot \text{velocity (m/s)} \cdot \text{wavelength (m)}$.

If we take the velocity to be the speed of light c , and the wavelength to be the circumference of the 1s orbital $2\pi r_{1s}$, so that the matter wave does not interfere with itself, then we find that the only factor missing to arrive at the exact value of h is the fine structure constant.

$$h_e = m_e c 2 \pi r_{1s} \alpha_f = 6.62607015E - 34 \frac{kg m^2}{s}$$

The value for h_e can also be reached with an equation replacing the Bohr radius r_{1s} with the classical radius of the electron r_e .

$$\text{Since } r_{1s} \alpha_f^2 = r_e \quad \text{therefore} \quad h_e = m_e c 2 \pi r_e \left(\frac{1}{\alpha_f} \right).$$

The next step is to derive an equation for the fine structure constant α_f . The standard equation for α_f is derived from the following constants:

$$\alpha_f = \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 \hbar c} = \frac{e^2}{2 \epsilon_0 h c}$$

To derive an equation for α_f , I find that the function of the mass surface density of the universe over the mass surface density of the proton emerges.

It is in fact of the same for as the function from Section II for the ratio of mass surface density of the observable universe over the mass surface density of the galaxy as the local system. By replacing the local mass m_L and local radius r_L of the function of equation of Section II, with the mass of the proton m_p and the radius of the proton r_p , I can arrive, with only a modification of the factor $1/2\pi$ for $\pi/2$, at an equation for a precise dimensionless calculation of α_f .

$$\text{Function for modified gravitational dynamics} \quad \frac{1}{2\pi} \frac{r_L^2}{R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_L}$$

$$\text{Fine structure constant} \quad \alpha_f = \frac{\pi}{2} \frac{r_p^2}{R_u^2} \frac{M_u}{m_p} = 7.297352569300E - 03 \text{ (dimensionless)}$$

Sommerfeld remarked on the coincidence that α_f seemed to be equal to the velocity of the electron v_e in the 1s orbital of hydrogen divided by the speed of light c . By using the standard equation $v_e = \frac{n h}{2\pi m_e r_{1s}}$ where n is the quantum number for the orbit of the electron, in this case $n=1$, and replacing with my equation for h for the electron, I can derive a precise confirmation of Sommerfeld's proposal.

$$\text{Since } v_e = \frac{1 (m_e c 2 \pi r_{1s} \alpha_f)}{2\pi m_e r_{1s}} = c \alpha_f = 2.18769126364306E + 06 \text{ m/s}$$

$$\text{Therefore} \quad \alpha_f = \frac{v_e}{c}$$

By using the same analogy and mathematical structure of angular momentum for the proton as for the electron, I can reach an exact equation for the Planck constant for the proton h_p . It should be noted that others have already noted in the past that this equation seemed to give a very good approximation (Unzicker, 2022). I propose here that it may in fact be an exact equation and a necessary condition of the internal consistency of the equations proposed in this paper.

$$h_p = m_p c 2 \pi r_p \frac{1}{4} = 6.62607015E - 34 \frac{kg m^2}{s}$$

The equivalence of the equations of value of h from the electron and the proton provides two additional equivalent equations for calculating α_f . The equivalence of these equations means that it is possible to calculate the value of the fine structure constant α_f both from the ratio of the mass per surface area of the universe over that of the proton, and also from the ratio of the angular momentum of the proton and that of the electron.

$$\text{Since } h_e = h_p \text{ therefore } \frac{\frac{1}{4} m_p c 2 \pi r_p}{m_e c 2 \pi r_{1s}} = \alpha_f$$

$$\text{Therefore } \alpha_f = \frac{\pi r_p^2 M_u}{2 R_u^2 m_p} = \frac{1 m_p r_p}{4 m_e r_{1s}} = 7.2973525693E - 03$$

$$\text{And since } r_e = r_{1s} \alpha_f^2 \text{ therefore } \alpha_f = 4 \frac{m_e r_e}{m_p r_p} = 7.2973525693E - 03$$

$$\alpha_f = \frac{m_p c 2 \pi r_p \frac{1}{4}}{m_e c 2 \pi r_{1s}} = \frac{1 m_p r_p}{4 m_e r_{1s}} = 4 \frac{m_e r_e}{m_p r_p} = 7.2973525693E - 03$$

Finally, Spin is a known characteristic of electrons and protons understood to behave as intrinsic angular momentum quantized to the allowed values of $\pm \frac{1}{2}$. The equations for the value of h from the electron and the proton can be used to calculate the magnitude of their spin S by the standard equation of $S = \pm \frac{1}{2} \hbar$ to describe the magnitude of spin S_e for the electron and S_p for proton.

$$\text{For the electron: } \text{Since } S_e = \pm \frac{1}{2} \frac{h_e}{2\pi} \text{ then } S_e = \pm \frac{1}{2} m_e c r_{1s} \alpha_f = \pm \frac{1}{2} m_e c r_e \frac{1}{\alpha_f}$$

$$\text{And for the proton: } \text{Since } S_p = \pm \frac{1}{2} \frac{h_p}{2\pi} \text{ then } S_p = \pm \frac{1}{8} m_p c r_p$$

Mass Ratio of Proton and Electron

Applying the equations for α_f from above, I find that it is possible to calculate the dimensionless proton-electron mass ratio.

$$\text{Since } \alpha_f = \frac{\pi r_p^2 M_u}{2 R_u^2 m_p} = \frac{1 m_p r_p}{4 m_e r_{1s}} = 4 \frac{m_e r_e}{m_p r_p}$$

$$\text{Therefore } \frac{m_p}{m_e} = \sqrt{2\pi \frac{r_{1s}}{r_p} \frac{r_p^2 M_u}{R_u^2 m_e}} \text{ and } \frac{m_p}{m_e} = 4 \frac{r_{1s}}{r_p} \alpha_f \text{ and } \frac{m_p}{m_e} = 4 \frac{r_e}{r_p} \frac{1}{\alpha_f}$$

$$\text{In all cases } \frac{m_p}{m_e} = 1,836.15267343918 \text{ (dimensionless)}$$

Therefore, I find that the mass of the proton can be calculated in terms of the mass of the electron and the ratio of the radii of the electron and the proton.

$$m_p = 4 m_e \frac{r_{1s}}{r_p} \alpha_f = 4 m_e \frac{r_e}{r_p} \frac{1}{\alpha_f} = 4 m_e \frac{\sqrt{r_{1s} r_e}}{r_p} = 1.67262192369251E - 27 \text{ kg}$$

Elementary Charge e, Vacuum Permittivity ϵ_0 and Vacuum Permeability μ_0

To derive the equations for the elementary charge e, vacuum permittivity ϵ_0 and vacuum permeability μ_0 I will start with a hypothesis. We know that protons and electrons behave as if they have intrinsic angular momentum (spin) even when “classically” at rest, meaning the electron or proton as a whole does not have a relative velocity with respect to an observer’s reference frame. My hypothesis is that charge, as the source of the energy for electromagnetism, may be described as intrinsic linear momentum. Therefore, charge would arise from intrinsic kinetic energy which all protons and electrons have due to their wave nature, even when at rest “classically”.

The energy-momentum relation equation for the total relativistic energy E_t of an object includes both its rest energy and its kinetic energy is $E_t^2 = (mc^2)^2 + (pc)^2$. If I assume that charge arises as kinetic energy due to a proton or electron’s linear momentum tangential to its angular momentum, then I need an equation with the units of $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$ derived from their equations for the reduced Planck constant \hbar or equivalently from their equations for Spin S. Using this dimensional analysis, we can reach the following equation for the charge of the proton e_p and the electron e_e with units of linear momentum.

$$\text{Since } h_e = m_e c 2 \pi r_e \frac{1}{\alpha_f} \quad \text{then}$$

$$e_e = -\frac{\hbar_e}{\frac{1}{4}\pi r_p} = -\frac{S_e}{\frac{1}{8}\pi r_p} = -4 m_e c \frac{r_e}{\pi r_p} \frac{1}{\alpha_f} = -1.59613130376877E - 19 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}/\text{s}$$

$$\text{And since } h_p = m_p c 2 \pi r_p \frac{1}{4}$$

$$e_p = \frac{\hbar_p}{\frac{1}{4}\pi r_p} = \frac{S_p}{\frac{1}{8}\pi r_p} = \frac{m_p c}{\pi} = 1.59613130376877E - 19 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}/\text{s}$$

I note here that this result varies from the standard CODATA values ($\sim 99.623\%$). However, the definition of the magnitude of the elementary charge e is exact by definition (without uncertainty values) because it is currently derived from the value of the vacuum permittivity ϵ_0 or the vacuum permeability μ_0 and the fine structure constant α_f by the following equation. The values for h and c are also exact by definition. Therefore, the uncertainties originate from the values of ϵ_0 or μ_0 and α_f .

$$e^2 = \frac{2 h \alpha_f}{\mu_0 c} = 2 h \alpha_f \epsilon_0 c$$

Therefore, I propose that the combination of e and of ϵ_0 or μ_0 may be more fundamental. To explore this, I will apply the equations derived this far to derive the equations for ϵ_0 and μ_0 .

$$\text{Since } \alpha_f = \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 \hbar c} = \frac{e^2}{2 \epsilon_0 h c} \quad \text{and} \quad c^2 = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0 \mu_0}$$

$$\text{And since } e_p = \frac{m_p c}{\pi} \quad \text{and} \quad e_e = -4 m_e c \frac{r_e}{\pi r_p} \frac{1}{\alpha_f}$$

$$\text{Therefore } \epsilon_0 = \frac{e_p^2}{2 h_p c \alpha_f} = \frac{\left(\frac{m_p c}{\pi}\right)^2}{2 (m_p c 2 \pi r_p \frac{1}{4}) c \alpha_f} = \frac{\frac{m_p c}{\pi}}{\pi^2 r_p c \alpha_f} = \frac{e_p}{\pi^2 r_p c \alpha_f}$$

$$\text{And } \epsilon_0 = \frac{e_e^2}{2 h_e c \alpha_f} = \frac{\left(4 m_e c \frac{r_e}{\pi r_p} \frac{1}{\alpha_f}\right)^2}{2 (m_e c 2 \pi r_{1s} \alpha_f) c \alpha_f} = \frac{4 m_e c \frac{r_e}{\pi r_p} \frac{1}{\alpha_f}}{\pi^2 r_p c \alpha_f} = \frac{e_e}{\pi^2 r_p c \alpha_f}$$

$$\text{Therefore } \epsilon_0 = \frac{e}{\pi^2 r_p c \alpha_f} = \frac{m_p}{\pi^3 r_p \alpha_f} = \frac{4 m_e}{\pi^3 r_p \alpha_f^2} \frac{r_e}{r_p}$$

$$\text{And } \epsilon_0 = \frac{e}{\pi^2 r_p c \alpha_f} = 8.7874966563885E - 12 \frac{kg}{m}$$

This result also varies from the standard CODATA values (~99.623%). It varies in fact by the exact equal amount as the value for elementary charge e. When I combine the equations for e and ϵ_0 as they are used for calculating the electromagnetic force, the discrepancy therefore disappears, and a physically meaningful equation is found. I will tentatively note the combined equations as β_e .

$$\text{Using SI values } \beta_e = \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0} = 2.30707755234174E - 28$$

$$\text{For two electrons } \beta_e = \frac{\left(4 m_e c \frac{r_e}{\pi r_p} \frac{1}{\alpha_f}\right)^2}{4 \pi \left(\frac{e}{\pi^2 r_p c \alpha_f}\right)} = m_e c^2 r_e = 2.30707755234868E - 28 kg \frac{m^2}{s^2} m$$

$$\text{For two protons } \beta_e = \frac{\left(\frac{m_p c}{\pi}\right)^2}{4 \pi \left(\frac{e}{\pi^2 r_p c \alpha_f}\right)} = \frac{1}{4} m_p c^2 r_p \alpha_f = 2.30707755234868E - 28 kg \frac{m^2}{s^2} m$$

I find that the results match within the inherent uncertainties. The final equations seem to indicate that the source of the electrostatic force is in fact the product of the electron and the proton rest mass energies mc^2 and their radii. Moreover, α_f emerges to provide the equality of magnitude of electrostatic force for electrons and for protons.

$$\text{Since } \beta_e = m_e c^2 r_e = \frac{1}{4} m_p c^2 r_p \alpha_f$$

$$\text{Therefore } \alpha_f = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{\frac{1}{4} m_p c^2 r_p} = 4 \frac{m_e r_e}{m_p r_p}$$

It is well known that the reduced Compton wavelength of an electron λ_e is $\lambda_e = \frac{\hbar}{m_e c}$. Conversely, the reduced Compton wavelength of a proton λ_p would be $\lambda_p = \frac{\hbar}{m_p c}$. I find that the product of these reduced Compton wavelengths and the fine structure constant results in the radii of the electrostatic force defined by β_e .

$$\text{For the electron } \lambda_e \alpha_f = \frac{\hbar_e}{m_e c} \alpha_f = \frac{m_e c r_e}{m_e c} \frac{1}{\alpha_f} \alpha_f = r_e$$

$$\text{For the proton} \quad \lambda_p \alpha_f = \frac{\hbar_p}{m_p c} \alpha_f = \frac{m_p c r_p}{m_p c} \frac{1}{4} \alpha_f = \frac{1}{4} r_p \alpha_f$$

$$\text{Therefore} \quad \beta_e = m_e c^2 \lambda_e \alpha_f = m_p c^2 \lambda_p \alpha_f$$

Given the equation ϵ_0 , I can derive the equation for the vacuum magnetic permeability μ_0 . I find that c^2 will cancel out of the equation when combined with the elementary charge squared e^2 , and once again, the combination of e^2 and μ_0 provides a precise result well within the inherent uncertainties of μ_0 .

$$\text{Since} \quad \mu_0 = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0 c^2}$$

$$\text{Therefore} \quad \mu_0 = \frac{1}{\epsilon_0 c^2} = \frac{\pi^2 r_p \alpha_f}{e c} = 1.26617408752551E - 06 \frac{1}{\text{kg} \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}^2}}$$

$$\text{For two electrons using SI values} \quad \frac{\mu_0 e^2}{4 \pi} = 2.56696996793297E - 45$$

$$\text{Therefore} \quad \frac{\mu_0 e^2}{4 \pi} = \frac{\pi^2 r_p \alpha_f}{e c} \frac{\left(4 m_e c \frac{r_e}{\pi r_p \alpha_f}\right)^2}{4 \pi} = m_e r_e = \frac{\beta_e}{c^2}$$

$$\text{And} \quad \frac{\mu_0 e^2}{4 \pi} = \frac{\beta_e}{c^2} = m_e r_e = 2.56696996794081E - 45 \text{ kg m}$$

Rydberg Constant

The Rydberg constant R_∞ is a well-known fundamental constant developed empirically by Rydberg and used for atomic spectra. It is one of the most accurately measured physical constants. Bohr demonstrated that it can be calculated from other fundamental constants. It is measured in units of wavenumber or inverse wavelength as m^{-1} . One of the most common equations for calculating R_∞ is the following with the CODATA 2018 value.

$$\text{CODATA 2018 value for } R_\infty = 10,973,731.568160 (0.000021) \text{ m}^{-1}$$

$$\text{calculated with CODATA values } R_\infty = \frac{m_e e^4}{8 \epsilon_0^2 h^3 c} = 10,973,731.5680726 \text{ m}^{-1}$$

By applying the equations developed above and my adjusted values for the masses and radius of proton and electron, I find that multiple values cancel out. In this way, I reach the following simpler equation for calculating the value of R_∞ in precise agreement with the measurement reported in CODATA 2018.

$$\text{calculated with adjusted values} \quad R_\infty = \frac{m_e \alpha_f^2}{m_p \pi r_p} = 10,973,731.56816 \text{ m}^{-1}$$

It is in fact this equation that anchors the adjustments I made, all within uncertainties of CODATA 2018, of the masses and radius of the proton and electron as well as the proton electron mass ratio.

It is well known that the calculation of the constant for the atomic spectra of hydrogen, noted as R_H , requires a correction known as the reduced mass of the electron by the function $\frac{m_p}{m_e + m_p}$. I can

calculate the value of R_H using the CODATA values and the standard equation and compare to my equation applying my adjusted values for the masses and radius of the proton and electron. I find that I reach a precise agreement.

$$\text{with CODATA values} \quad R_H = R_\infty \frac{m_p}{m_e + m_p} = 10,967,758.3402804 \text{ m}^{-1}$$

$$\text{with adjusted values} \quad R_H = \frac{m_e}{m_e + m_p} \frac{\alpha_f^2}{\pi r_p} = 10,967,758.3402804 \text{ m}^{-1}$$

Units of classical electrodynamics

From all the equations to this point, I find that the units of classical electrodynamics can be expressed using only SI units of kilograms, meters and seconds. The units of charge would be those of momentum, mass times velocity: $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. If the units of charge are those of momentum, this would mean that the SI units of Coulombs (C) would also be $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$.

If I define Coulombs (C) as equivalent to units of momentum, then using dimensional analysis and Ohm's law of Current ($I = \text{Voltage (V)}/\text{Resistance (R)}$), I can derive the physical units for each of these. In terms of SI based units, Current (I) is measured in Amperes (A), Voltage (V) is measured in Volts (V), and Resistance (R) is measured in Ohms (Ω).

First, in SI units, Coulombs can be measured in Amperes and seconds: $C = A \cdot s$. Therefore, Amperes would be $A = \text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$. These are Newtons⁶, the units of force (mass \cdot acceleration). Therefore, in a physical sense, Current (I) would be a measure of the force applied to the system. Second, Volts (V) can be measured in Joules per Coulomb. Therefore, Volts would be $V = J/C = (\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^2\cdot\text{s}^{-2})/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}) = \text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}$. Therefore, Volts and Voltage (measured in Volts) would need to be a relative value, as is velocity, only meaningful when compared between two objects. And third, Resistance (R) with units of Ohms (Ω) can be measured in Volts per Ampere. Therefore, the units of Resistance, Ohms (Ω), can be converted to $\Omega = V/A = (\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1})/(\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}) = \text{s}/\text{kg}$. Therefore, Ohms would be a measure of units of time elapsed per unit of mass, or seconds per kilogram. Conversely, the inverse of resistance would be $1/\Omega$ which would have units of kilograms per second.

The resulting units for ϵ_0 are kilograms per meters $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$. The vacuum permittivity ϵ_0 currently is measured in Farads (F) per meter F/m, or conversely $\text{A}^2\cdot\text{s}^4\cdot\text{kg}^{-1}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$ in SI base units. We can see that replacing the SI units for Amperes (A) with $A = \text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, several units of the SI definition cancel out, and we reach the units of $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}^{-1}$ for ϵ_0 .

The resulting units for μ_0 are 1 over force. In terms of SI base units, μ_0 has the unit $\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}\cdot\text{A}^{-2}$, or in derived units it is Newtons over Amperes squared. I find that replacing the SI units for Amperes (A) with $A = \text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$, the Newtons in the numerator cancel out, and reach the units of $1/\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2}$ for μ_0 .

The SI unit for the electric field E is volts per meter (V/m). Applying the conversion from above, I find that the unit would become $E = (\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1})/\text{m} = 1/\text{s}$. The unit of the electric field would therefore be cycles per second.

⁶ Until 2019, the ampere was defined as the constant current which, if maintained in two straight parallel conductors of infinite length of negligible circular cross section and placed one metre apart in a vacuum, would produce between these conductors a force equal to $2E10^{-7}$ newton per metre of length. (Source: Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. "ampere". Encyclopaedia Britannica, 9 Mar. 2024)

The SI unit for the magnetic field B is Tesla or newtons per meter per ampere. Applying the conversion from above, I find that the unit would become $B=T=(\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2})/(\text{m}\cdot\text{kg}\cdot\text{m}\cdot\text{s}^{-2})=1/\text{m}$. The unit of the magnetic field would therefore be cycles per meter.

Electrostatic and Magnetic Forces

To derive the equation for the electrostatic force F_e , I will apply here the equations for charge e and vacuum permittivity ϵ_0 . The equation for two protons $F_{e_{2p}}$ at a distance d would be as follows.

$$\text{Since } \beta_e = \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0} = \frac{1}{4} m_p c^2 r_p \alpha_f$$

$$\text{Therefore } F_{e_{2p}} = \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d^2} = \frac{\beta_e}{d^2} = \frac{1}{4} \frac{m_p c^2 r_p}{d^2} \alpha_f \text{ (units: kg} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}\text{)}$$

The equation for the electrostatic force between two electrons $F_{e_{2e}}$ at a distance d using both the Bohr radius of the electron r_{1s} , and the classical radius of the electron r_e would be as follows.

$$\text{Since } \beta_e = \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0} = m_e c^2 r_e \quad \text{and} \quad r_e = r_{1s} \alpha_f^2$$

$$\text{Therefore } F_{e_{2e}} = \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d^2} = \frac{\beta_e}{d^2} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_{1s}}{d^2} \alpha_f^2 = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{d^2} \text{ (units: kg} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}\text{)}$$

The equation for the attractive electrostatic force between a proton and an electron would be of the same magnitude but opposite sign and can be expressed from the frame of reference of the proton or the electron. This is because the equation for the vacuum permittivity ϵ_0 includes the elementary charge e ($\epsilon_0 = \frac{e}{\pi^2 r_p c \alpha_f}$) and will always cancel out one of the e^2 in electromagnetic equations. If we have a case of multiple protons or electrons, the mass term in the equation can be quantized in terms of the product of the number of protons or electrons contained in each charge q, by the number of elementary charges e.

To derive the equation for the magnetic force, I will apply the equations for the elementary charge e and vacuum permeability μ_0 . For simplicity, I will derive the equation for two electrons e_1 and e_2 moving relative to each other with velocity v in opposite direction along parallel paths at a distance d. I will present the standard equations for calculating the magnetic field generated by the first electron e_1 from the reference frame of the second electron e_2 and those for calculating the magnetic force on this second electron due to its movement relative to the magnetic field.

The magnetic field B at the distance d, generated by the first electron e_1 moving at velocity v relative to the second electron's e_2 reference frame is determined by the following equation.

$$B = \frac{\mu_0 q v \sin \theta}{4\pi d^2} = \frac{\mu_0 e_1 v \sin \theta}{4\pi d^2}$$

Since the first electron's velocity vector is parallel to the second electron, the angle of the magnetic field will be at 90° , and therefore $\sin \theta = 1$.

$$\text{Since } \sin 90^\circ = 1 \quad \text{Therefore } B = \frac{\mu_0 e_1 v}{4\pi d^2}$$

The magnetic force F_m on the second electron e_2 from this magnetic field is determined by the following equation.

$$F_m = B q v \sin \theta \quad \text{and since} \quad \sin 90^\circ = 1 \quad \text{and} \quad B = \frac{\mu_0 e_1 v}{4\pi d^2}$$

$$\text{Therefore} \quad F_m = \left(\frac{\mu_0 e_1 v}{4\pi d^2} \right) e_2 v = \frac{\mu_0 e_1 e_2 v^2}{4\pi d^2}$$

$$\text{Since} \quad \frac{\mu_0 e^2}{4\pi} = \frac{\beta_e}{c^2} = m_e r_e$$

$$\text{Therefore} \quad F_m = \frac{\mu_0 e^2 v^2}{4\pi d^2} = \frac{\beta_e v^2}{d^2 c^2} = \frac{m_e r_e}{d^2} v^2$$

I reach an equation for magnetic force F_m which is exactly as the one for electrostatic force F_e replacing c^2 with $\frac{v^2}{c^2}$. Therefore, the following equation for the unified electromagnetic force F_{em} between these two electrons can be written.

$$\text{Since} \quad F_{em} = F_e + F_m = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{d^2} + \frac{m_e r_e v^2}{d^2}$$

$$\text{Therefore} \quad F_{em} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{d^2} \left(1 + \frac{v^2}{c^2} \right) = \frac{m_e r_e (c^2 + v^2)}{d^2}$$

I find that this equation reaches the same conclusion of special relativity that magnetism is in fact a relativistic correction of the electrostatic force due to relative movement. It seems that both electrostatic and magnetic forces are due to relative movement. The intrinsic momentum of matter waves manifests as charge and an electric field when it is at rest in the classical sense. When moving at a certain velocity in the classical sense, it will have an additional momentum and therefore force which manifests through what we define as the magnetic field.

Ratio of electrostatic force F_e to Newtonian gravitational force F_g

Describing the equations of electrostatic force in terms of the speed of light, masses and radii enables me to calculate the ratio of the electrostatic force F_e to Newtonian gravitational force F_g starting from the standard equations.

The equation for the ratio of $\frac{F_e}{F_g}$ for two protons at a distance d would be as follows. The electrostatic force is $F_{e_{2p}}$ and the Newtonian gravitational force is $F_{g_{2p}}$.

$$\text{Since} \quad F_{e_{2p}} = \frac{e^2}{4\pi \epsilon_0 d^2} = \frac{1}{4} \frac{m_p c^2 r_p}{d^2} \alpha_f$$

$$\text{And} \quad F_{g_{2p}} = \frac{G m_p^2}{d^2} = \frac{c^2 R_u m_p^2}{M_u d^2}$$

$$\text{Therefore} \quad \frac{F_{e_{2p}}}{F_{g_{2p}}} = \frac{e^2}{G m_p^2 4\pi \epsilon_0} = \frac{\frac{1}{4} m_p c^2 r_p \alpha_f}{\frac{c^2 R_u}{M_u} m_p^2} = \frac{1}{4} \frac{r_p M_u}{R_u m_p} \alpha_f$$

$$\text{And} \quad \frac{F_{e_{2p}}}{F_{g_{2p}}} = \frac{1}{4} \frac{r_p M_u}{R_u m_p} \alpha_f = 1.2355516357614E + 36 \text{ (dimensionless)}$$

The equation for the ratio of $\frac{F_e}{F_g}$ for two electrons at a distance d would be as follows.

$$\text{Since } F_{e_{2e}} = \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d^2} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{d^2}$$

$$\text{And } F_{g_{2e}} = \frac{G m_e^2}{d^2} = \frac{c^2 R_u m_e^2}{M_u d^2}$$

$$\text{Therefore } \frac{F_{e_{2e}}}{F_{g_{2e}}} = \frac{e^2}{G m_e^2 4 \pi \epsilon_0} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{\frac{c^2 R_u}{M_u} m_e^2} = \frac{r_e M_u}{R_u m_e} = \frac{r_{1s} M_u}{R_u m_e} \alpha_f^2$$

$$\text{And } \frac{F_{e_{2e}}}{F_{g_{2e}}} = \frac{r_e M_u}{R_u m_e} = 4.16560876667038E + 42(\text{dimensionless})$$

I find that I can calculate what seem to be the correct values of the ratios with high levels of precision. Moreover, the resulting equations for the ratios clearly show that the relative strength of electrostatic and gravitational forces arise from the ratios of the mass and radii of the proton, electron and those of the observable universe, in line with Dirac's intuition for his large number hypothesis.

Gravitational force from electrodynamic constants

Having reached the equations for electrodynamic constants above, and the ratio of the electrostatic and Newtonian gravitational forces, it is possible to describe the latter in terms of the former, and vice versa.

Therefore, the gravitational force can be calculated using electrodynamic constants (e , ϵ_0 , α_f) and the functions of $\frac{F_e}{F_g}$ without the gravitational constant G .

To illustrate this, I will derive the equation to calculate the gravitational force between the earth and an apple, and the acceleration g felt by the apple. I will use for the mass of the earth $m_E = 5.9722E+24$ kg and the equatorial radius $r_E = 6.378137E+06$ m. For the apple, I will use a mass of $m_a = 0.16$ kg. I will quantize the masses of the earth and the apple in terms of the mass of the electron by m_E/m_e and m_a/m_e to obtain the equivalent number of electrons in terms of mass.

$$\text{Since } \frac{F_{e_{2e}}}{F_{g_{2e}}} = \frac{r_e M_u}{R_u m_e} \quad \text{and} \quad F_{g_{2e}} = F_{e_{2e}} \frac{F_{g_{2e}}}{F_{e_{2e}}} = F_{e_{2e}} \frac{R_u m_e}{r_e M_u}$$

$$\text{Therefore } F_g = \frac{m_E m_a}{m_e^2} \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 r_E^2} \frac{R_u m_e}{r_e M_u} = \frac{m_E m_a}{m_e^2} \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{r_E^2} \frac{R_u m_e}{r_e M_u} = \frac{c^2 R_u m_E m_a}{M_u r_E^2}$$

$$\text{And } F_g = \frac{m_E m_a}{m_e^2} \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 r_E^2} \frac{R_u m_e}{r_e M_u} = G \frac{m_E m_a}{r_E^2} = 1.56773394713665 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$$

$$\text{Since } g = \frac{F_g}{m_a}$$

$$\text{Therefore acceleration on Earth } g_E = \frac{m_E}{m_e r_e} \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 r_E^2} \frac{R_u}{M_u} = 9.79833716960403 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}$$

The following comparison between the electrostatic and gravitational forces may be clearest to demonstrate the relationship between the forces of two bodies. Let us imagine a thought experiment with two imaginary systems. The first made of the earth and an apple made solely of electrons and therefore negatively charged. The second made of the earth and an apple as we know them, made up of atoms which are in aggregate electrically neutral.

The electrostatic force equation for the first system would have q_E for the earth of $q_E = e(m_E/m_e)$ and q_a for the apple of $q_a = e(m_a/m_e)$ at a distance of the equatorial radius r_E .

$$F_e = \frac{m_E}{m_e} \frac{m_a}{m_e} \frac{e^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 r_E^2} = \frac{m_E}{m_e} \frac{m_a}{m_e} \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{r_E^2} = \frac{m_E m_a c^2 r_e}{r_E^2 m_e}$$

The gravitational force equation would be the product of this equation and the proportionality function for $\frac{F_g}{F_e} = \frac{R_u m_e}{r_e M_u}$.

$$F_g = \frac{m_E m_a c^2 r_e}{r_E^2 m_e} \frac{R_u m_e}{r_e M_u} = \frac{m_E m_a c^2 R_u}{r_E^2 M_u}$$

It is clear to see the source of energy for both forces is the product of the masses and c^2 . In the case of the first system for electrostatic force, the resulting force is proportional to the ratio of the radius and mass of one electron $\frac{r_e}{m_e}$. In the case of the second system for gravitational force, the resulting force is the same basic equation and proportional to the ratio of the radius and mass of the observable universe $\frac{R_u}{M_u}$.

Therefore, the total force from electrostatic and gravitational interaction on a system of two bodies of mass m_1 and m_2 , at distance d , consisting each of only electrons would be described by the following equation.

$$\text{Since } F_e = \frac{m_1 m_2 c^2 r_e}{d^2 m_e} \quad \text{and} \quad F_g = \frac{m_1 m_2 c^2 R_u}{d^2 M_u}$$

$$\text{Therefore } F_T \quad F_T = F_e - F_g = \frac{m_1 m_2 c^2 r_e}{d^2 m_e} - \frac{m_1 m_2 c^2 R_u}{d^2 M_u}$$

$$\text{Therefore the total force } F_T = F_e - F_g = \frac{m_1 m_2 c^2}{d^2} \left(\frac{r_e}{m_e} - \frac{R_u}{M_u} \right)$$

The electrostatic force of two protons is equal in magnitude as between two electrons despite their different masses (by $\sim 1,836$) because their net charge is equal in number, but of opposite sign. This means that the proton, known to be a composite particle, is made up of constituents which add up to the rest mass energy of the proton, and leave a net charge which must be equivalent with a charged particle with the mass of the electron and of opposite sign: a positron.

To conclude this section, I find the results from this work may demonstrate the interconnectedness of the physics at atomic and cosmological scales. Dirac tells us: "*such a coincidence we may presume is due to some deep connection in nature between cosmology and atomic theory.*" It seems to be in fact the fine structure constant, through the ratios it precisely quantifies, which is at the centre of this deep connection of physics from the smallest to the largest scales. Dirac's large number hypothesis may not have been quantitatively precise, but I believe his intuition was pointing in the correct direction.

Section IV: On a relation between α_f and the relative strengths and ranges of nuclear forces

In this section, I will present unexpected findings which emerged from the derived equations for the electrostatic force. I did not originally intend to delve into nuclear physics in this work. However, the findings perhaps do merit this brief outline. Once again, I find that the ratio of the mass surface density of the universe over that of the proton is a determining function.

From the equations for electrostatic force in the previous section, I find that the equations for the electrostatic potential energy U_e equation would predict that, at specific distances d , U_e will equal the rest mass energy of the electron and of the proton. Moreover, these distances seem to be directly related to the ranges of nuclear forces. Finally, I find that it is the product of the reduced Compton wavelengths and the fine structure constant that provides the distances at which the nuclear forces operate as presented here.

$$\text{For the electron:} \quad \text{Since} \quad \lambda_e \alpha_f = \frac{\hbar_e}{m_e c} \alpha_f = \frac{m_e c r_e}{m_e c} \frac{1}{\alpha_f} \alpha_f = r_e$$

$$\text{And} \quad \lambda_e \alpha_f = r_{1s} \alpha_f^2 = r_e = 2.81794032620793E - 15 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Therefore with } d = r_e \quad U_E = \frac{q^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{r_e} = m_e c^2$$

$$\text{For the proton:} \quad \text{Since} \quad \lambda_p \alpha_f = \frac{\hbar_p}{m_p c} \alpha_f = \frac{m_p c r_p}{m_p c} \frac{1}{4} \alpha_f = \frac{1}{4} r_p \alpha_f$$

$$\text{And} \quad \lambda_p \alpha_f = \frac{1}{4} r_p \alpha_f = 1.53469826718158E - 18$$

$$\text{Therefore with } d = \frac{1}{4} r_p \alpha_f \quad U_E = \frac{q^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d} = \frac{1}{4} \frac{m_p c^2 r_p \alpha_f}{\frac{1}{4} r_p \alpha_f} = m_p c^2$$

This would seem to indicate that nuclear forces have an intriguing connection with electromagnetism, the Compton wavelengths of the electron and the proton, and the rest mass energy of these matter waves.

The following equation shows that when two electrons are a distance $d = r_{1s} \alpha_f^2 = r_e = 2.80730767839722E - 15 \text{ m}$ (~ 2.8 fermi), then the electrostatic potential energy equals the rest mass energy of the electron: $U_E = m_e c^2$. This distance is the known approximate distance at which the nuclear strong force starts to become significant.

$$U_E = \frac{q^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{r_e} = m_e c^2$$

At a distance of half r_e when $d = \frac{1}{2} r_{1s} \alpha_f^2 = \frac{1}{2} r_e = 1.40897016310396E-15 \text{ m}$ (~ 1.4 fermi), I reach a value within the range of the estimates for the constant r_0 (between 1.2 to 1.5 fermi), used to calculate the radius of a nucleus R by $R = r_0 A^{1/3}$ with A being the nucleon number. At this range, the electrostatic potential energy is equal to twice the rest mass energy of the electron.

$$U_E = \frac{q^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{\frac{1}{2} r_e} = 2 m_e c^2$$

At a distance of one quarter r_e when $d = \frac{1}{4} r_{1s} \alpha_f^2 = \frac{1}{4} r_e = 7.04485081551982E - 16 m$ (~ 0.7 fermi), we reach the range at which the nuclear strong force becomes repulsive. At this range, the electrostatic potential energy would be equal to four times the rest mass energy of the electron.

$$U_E = \frac{q^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{\frac{1}{4} r_e} = 4 m_e c^2$$

At a distance equal to the radius of the proton, when $d = r_p = r_e \frac{4 m_e}{m_p} \frac{1}{\alpha_f} = 8.412356413409760E - 16 m$ (~ 0.84 fermi), the strong force is known to approximate its peak attractive strength between nucleons. At this distance, the electrostatic potential energy would be equal to the rest mass energy of the electron and the ratio of the radii of the electron and the proton.

$$\text{Since } r_p = r_e \frac{4 m_e}{m_p} \frac{1}{\alpha_f} \quad \text{and} \quad \alpha_f = 4 \frac{m_e r_e}{m_p r_p}$$

$$\text{Therefore } U_E = \frac{q^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{r_p} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{r_e \frac{4 m_e}{m_p} \frac{1}{\alpha_f}} = \frac{1}{4} m_p c^2 \alpha_f$$

$$\text{And } U_E = \frac{1}{4} m_p c^2 \alpha_f = \frac{1}{4} m_p c^2 \left(4 \frac{m_e r_e}{m_p r_p} \right) = m_e c^2 \frac{r_e}{r_p}$$

At a distance when $d = \frac{1}{4} r_p \alpha_f = 1.53469826718158000E - 18 m$ (~ 0.0015 fermi), the weak nuclear force is expected to be of similar magnitude to electromagnetic force. At this distance, the electrostatic potential energy would be equal to the rest mass energy of the proton.

$$\text{Since } U_E = \frac{q^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d} = \frac{1 m_p c^2 r_p}{4 d} \alpha_f$$

$$\text{When } d = \frac{1}{4} r_p \alpha_f = r_e \frac{m_e}{m_p} = 1.53469826718158000E - 18 m (\sim 0.0015 \text{ fermi})$$

$$\text{Therefore } U_E = \frac{q^2}{4 \pi \epsilon_0 d} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{\frac{1}{4} r_p \alpha_f} = \frac{m_e c^2 r_e}{r_e \frac{m_e}{m_p}} = m_p c^2$$

Relative Strength of Four Fundamental Forces

The relative strength and ranges of the four fundamental forces is known empirically to be the following approximate values using the Strong force as the base 1.

Force	Relative Strength (base Strong Nuclear)	Range (metres)
Strong	1	10^{-15} increasing $\propto r$
Electromagnetic	$\sim 1/137$	∞ decreasing $\propto 1/r^2$
Weak	$\sim 10^{-5}$	10^{-18} decreasing $\propto 1/r$
Gravitation	$\sim 6 \times 10^{-39}$	∞ decreasing $\propto 1/r^2$

I find that these ranges can be arrived at with the following functions. I have differentiated gravitation for protons and for electrons as we know that the relative strength of gravitation to electromagnetic force is different for each of them. The gravitational coupling constant α_g used below defined as $\alpha_g = \frac{F_g}{F_e} \alpha_f$. Noting that the ratio of gravitational to electromagnetic force for two protons $F_{g_{2p}}$ and two electrons $F_{g_{2e}}$ was derived in the previous section as follows.

$$\text{for two protons} \quad \frac{F_{g_{2p}}}{F_{e_{2p}}} = 4 \frac{R_u m_p}{r_p M_u} \frac{1}{\alpha_f}$$

$$\text{for two electrons} \quad \frac{F_{g_{2e}}}{F_{e_{2e}}} = \frac{R_u m_e}{r_e M_u}$$

Using the strong force F_s as the base 1, I find that the ratios of the electromagnetic force F_e , the weak force F_w , and the gravitational force for two protons $F_{g_{2p}}$ and two electrons $F_{g_{2e}}$ to the strong force are the following.

With Strong Force = 1

$$\text{Electromagnetic} \quad \frac{F_e}{F_s} = \alpha_f = 7.2973525693E - 03$$

$$\text{Weak} \quad \frac{F_w}{F_s} = \frac{1}{4} \alpha_f^2 = 1.33128386301673E - 05$$

$$\text{Gravitational (protons)} \quad \frac{F_{g_{2p}}}{F_s} = \alpha_g \alpha_f = \frac{F_{g_{2p}}}{F_e} \alpha_f = 4 \frac{R_u m_p}{r_p M_u} = 5.9061494138228E - 39$$

$$\text{Gravitational (electrons)} \quad \frac{F_{g_{2e}}}{F_s} = \alpha_g \alpha_f = \frac{F_{g_{2e}}}{F_e} \alpha_f = \frac{R_u m_e}{r_e M_u} \alpha_f = 1.75180939402835E - 45$$

One can see that the fine structure constant α_f seems to act as a proportionality factor between the forces. It is possible to rearrange the above ratios using electromagnetic force as the base 1. As can be seen below, this results in a clear hierarchy of functions.

With Electromagnetic Force = 1

$$\text{Strong} \quad \frac{F_s}{F_e} = \frac{1}{\alpha_f} = 137.035999083696$$

$$\text{Weak} \quad \frac{F_w}{F_e} = \frac{1}{4} \alpha_f = 1.824338142325E - 03$$

$$\text{Gravitational (protons)} \quad \frac{F_{g_{2p}}}{F_e} = 4 \frac{R_u m_p}{r_p M_u} \frac{1}{\alpha_f} = 8.09355085660792E - 37$$

$$\text{Gravitational (electrons)} \quad \frac{F_{g_{2e}}}{F_e} = \frac{R_u m_e}{r_e M_u} = 2.40060950514878E - 43$$

These equations seem to say that the ratio of strengths of the four forces of physics is determined by the function which emerges from the ratio of the mass surface density of the universe over that of the proton α_f .

The coincidence of these results with the approximate ranges and relative strengths of the forces known empirically are certainly encouraging. However, I find I have now ventured in far deeper waters than my knowledge and understanding allows for responsibly. Therefore, I will pause here and hope that this work to explore the origin of fundamental constants, if found to be correct, may prove insightful for our understanding of physical reality.

Acknowledgments

I thank first my wife, Therese Cregan, whose patience, and generosity allowed me to dedicate much of my time and focus to this work in the past nine years. I thank Electrical Engineer Fuad Dzafić for our long conversations during the past four years, his feedback and guidance, and for sharing generously his knowledge of mathematics and physical insights. I thank Physicist Professor Dragan Hajduković for his kindness in reviewing this work, for his useful suggestions, and for his reassurance to move forward. I thank Dr. Carver Mead for his generosity in reading the draft, taking the time to share with me both insightful feedback and encouragement. I thank all my friends and family who, during all these years, graciously listened to my thoughts, shared with me their reflections, and encouraged me to complete this work.

References

- Banik, I. (2024). Strong constraints on the gravitational law from Gaia DR3 wide binaries. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, Volume 527, issue 3, pages 4573 - 4615.
- Dicke, R. H. (1961). Mach's Principle and Invariance under Transformation of Units. *Physical Review*, 125(6), 2163-2167.
- Dirac, P. A. (1937). A new basis for cosmology. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A*, Vol. 165, pp. 199-208.
- Eddington, A. S. (1938). The Constants of Nature. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, Vol. 98, pp. 334-352.
- Einstein, A. (1905). Ist die Trägheit eines Körpers von seinem Energieinhalt abhängig? [Does the Inertia of a Body Depend Upon Its Energy Content?]. *Annalen der Physik*, 17(8), 891-921.
- Einstein, A. (1911). "Über die Wirkung der Schwere auf die Ausbreitung des Lichtes.". *Annalen der Physik*, 35(10), 898-908.
- Einstein, A. (1912). Gibt es eine Gravitationswirkung, die der elektrodynamischen Induktionswirkung ähnlich ist? *Physikalische Zeitschrift*, 13, 318-320.
- Einstein, A. (1916). Die Grundlage der allgemeinen Relativitätstheorie. *Annalen der Physik*, 354(7), 769-822.
- Eite Tiesinga, P. J. (2021). CODATA recommended values of the fundamental physical constants: 2018. *Reviews of Modern Physics*, 93, 025010.
- Fixsen, D. J. (2007). The Cosmic Microwave Background Spectrum from the Full COBE FIRAS Data Set. *The Astrophysical Journal*, vol. 655, pp. 980-992.
- Fukugita, M. H. (1998). The cosmic baryon budget. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 503(2), 518-530.
- Hill, C. J. (2021). Evidence for Cosmic Variance in the Local Hubble Constant from the Dark Energy Survey. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 908(1), 39.
- Labbé, I. v. (2023). A population of red candidate massive galaxies ~600 Myr after the Big Bang. *Nature* 616, 266–269.
- Mach, E. (1883). Die Mechanik in ihrer Entwicklung: Historisch-kritisch dargestellt. *Leipzig: F.A. Brockhaus*.
- McCulloch, M. (2017). Low-acceleration dwarf galaxies as tests of quantised inertia. *Astrophysics and Space Science*, 362. 10.1007/s10509-017-3039-6.
- McGaugh, S. S. (2016). The Radial Acceleration Relation in Rotationally Supported Galaxies. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 818(1), 1.
- Menanteau, F. H. (2012). THE ATACAMA COSMOLOGY TELESCOPE: ACT-CL J0102–4915 "EL GORDO," A MASSIVE MERGING CLUSTER AT REDSHIFT 0.87. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 748, 7.
- Milgrom, M. (1983). A modification of the Newtonian dynamics as a possible alternative to the hidden mass hypothesis. *The Astrophysical Journal*, 270, 365-370.
- Milgrom, M. (2008). Marriage à-la-MOND: Baryonic dark matter in galaxy clusters and the cooling flow puzzle. *New Astronomy Reviews*, Volume 51, Issues 10–12, 2008, p.906-915.

- Milgrom, M. (2015). Ultra-diffuse cluster galaxies as key to the MOND cluster conundrum. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, Volume 454, Issue 4, 21 December 2015, Pages 3810–3815.
- Morel, L. Y. (2020). Determination of the fine-structure constant with an accuracy of 81 parts per trillion. *Nature* 588, 61–65.
- Peebles, P. J. (1982). The Origin of the Cosmic Microwave Background. *The Astrophysical Journal*, vol. 263, pp. L1-L5.
- Planck Collaboration. (2016). Planck 2015 results. XIII. Cosmological parameters. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 594, A13.
- Planck Collaboration. (2020). Planck 2018 results. VI. Cosmological parameters. *Astronomy & Astrophysics*, 641, A6.
- Riess, A. G. (2022). A Comprehensive Measurement of the Local Value of the Hubble Constant with 1 km s⁻¹ Mpc⁻¹ Uncertainty from the Hubble Space Telescope and the SH0ES Team. *Astrophysical Journal Letters*, Volume 934 L7.
- Rodney, S. A.-G. (2012). The Discovery of the Most Distant Known Type Ia Supernova at Redshift 1.914. *The Astrophysical Journal Letters*, 746(1), L5.
- Scarpa, R. (2006). Modified Newtonian Dynamics, an Introductory Review. *AIP Conference Proceedings 21 March 2006*, 822 (1): 253–265.
- Schrödinger, E. (1925). Die Erfüllbarkeit der Relativitätsforderung in der klassischen Mechanik. *Annalen der Physik*, 382. 325-336.
- Sciama, D. W. (1953). On the Origin of Inertia. *Monthly Notices of the Royal Astronomical Society*, 113(1), 34-42.
- Unzicker, A. (2022). *Einstein's Lost Key*. CreateSpace.
- Zhang, S.-N. Y. (2012). On a common misunderstanding of the Birkhoff theorem and light deflection calculation: generalized Shapiro delay and its possible laboratory test. *International Journal of Modern Physics Conference Series*.